

VIRTUAL MEMORY MANAGEMENT VISUALIZATION ALGORITHMS

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Modern information technologies are one of the main components of educational technologies. Without their use, the progress of pedagogical science is practically impossible. The development of software simulators characterizes the latest period of pedagogy development. Their use increases students' intellectual abilities, mental potential, etc. [1].

Modern computer technologies can successfully teach processes invisible to the human eye. Such an area includes functions performed by the operating system kernel, the visualization and display of which on the monitor is an important step towards their successful teaching [2].

Keywords: Virtual memory, visualization algorithms.

Virtual memory management contains the following strategies for unloading pages from RAM: random page unloading, first in first out (FIFO), least recently unused page unloading (LRU), least frequently used page unloading (LFU), and not recently used page unloading (NRU) [1].

Random page unloading. In this case, all pages in RAM can be selected with equal probability. In this sense, this strategy does not discriminate against any page. On the other hand, a page that could be accessed in a short time can be unloaded from RAM.

FIFO (First in, First Out). This principle assigns a timestamp to each page when it enters RAM. The page that has been in memory the longest will be unloaded. The argument for this strategy is that a particular page has had a chance to be used, and it is time to give that chance to other pages. On the other hand, if a page has been in RAM for a long time, it may mean that it is in constant use.

LRU (Least Recently Unused Page Unload). This strategy will unload the page that has not been used for the longest time. This strategy requires that the page timestamp be updated each time it is accessed. Also,

this strategy can unload a page that has not been used for a long time and then force the same page to be immediately loaded into memory.

LFU (Least Frequently Used Page). This strategy determines how intensively each page is used. The page that is used the least or referenced the least will be unloaded. The disadvantage of this strategy is that the least-used page may be the one that was just loaded into RAM and accessed only once, while other pages have been accessed several times.

NRU (Not Recently Used Page Unloading). The essence of this strategy is that pages that have not been used in the last period will not be accessed soon, meaning they can be unloaded from RAM.

To model virtual memory management, we must make the following assumptions [3]:

1. We know the sequence in which each page enters the system.
2. We know the size of memory that the operating system allocates for each page.

Based on these assumptions, we can represent the pending pages as the following sequence:

$G_1(n_1, z_1)$	$G_2(n_2, z_2)$	$G_3(n_3, z_3)$...	$G_i(n_i, z_i)$	*
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The first element of this sequence contains information about the first page, the second element - about the second page, and so on. The sequence element usually has the form - $G_i(n_i, z_i)$. Here, G_i is the number of

$G_1(1, 8)$	$G_2(2, 15)$	$G_3(3, 11)$	$G_2(4, 17)$	$G_4(5, 5)$	*
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The first element of the sequence is " $G_1(1,8)$ " This means that the first reference is made to page G_1 . Its' size is 8 megabytes. Page G_1 will be placed into RAM immediately if there is a free area in memory. If there is no free area in memory, then according to some strategy, one of the pages will be unloaded from memory, and page G_1 will be loaded instead. The second element of the queue contains page G_2 . Its size is 15 megabytes. If there is no free area in memory, then according to some strategy, one of the pages will be unloaded from

the i -th page. n_i is the G_i page usage order. The G_i page occupies an area of z_i size of RAM. Let's discuss an example. Let's assume we have the following sequence of pages:

memory, and page G_2 will be loaded instead. As seen from the sequence, the same page will be accessed after the third page has been accessed. Finally, the fourth page will be accessed.

Denote the maximum number of pages by N^{\max} . Let A_s denote the initial address of the RAM area occupied by the page. Let A_e denote the last address of the RAM area occupied by the page. Accordingly, the initial address of the RAM area occupied by page G_1 will

be A_{s1} , and the last address will be A_{e1} . The initial address of the RAM area occupied by page G_2 will be A_{s2} , and the last address will be A_{e2} , and so on. The final address of the RAM area occupied by page G_i is determined as follows: $A_{ei} = A_{si} + Z_i$.

Strategies for unloading pages from RAM can be modeled as follows.

Strategy "Random page unloading". A free memory area sufficient for placing the page G_i is allocated. If there is no free memory area, a randomly selected page G_j ($i \neq j$) is unloaded, and the requested page G_i is loaded instead.

FIFO strategy. A free memory area is allocated for the page G_i , where it will be placed. If there is no free area in RAM, then the first entered page G_j among the entered pages ($i \neq j$) will be unloaded, and the requested page G_i will be loaded instead. Each page G_i has a number - h_i . The first page is considered to be the page for which this number has a minimum value: $h^{\min}_k = \min \{ h_1, h_2, h_3, \dots, h_j \}$.

LRU strategy. In this case, each page has a time counter t_i , which records the time that has passed since the page was used. A free memory area is allocated for the page G_i , where it will be placed. If there is no free area in memory, the page that has not been used for the longest time G_j ($i \neq j$) will be unloaded, and the requested page G_i will be loaded instead. The longest time unused page is the page for which the time counter has the greatest value: $t^{\max}_k = \max \{ t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_j \}$.

LFU strategy. In this case, each page has its own M_i usage counter, which records the number of times the page is used. For the G_i page, a free memory area is allocated in which it will be placed. If there is no free area in memory, then the rarely used page G_j ($i \neq j$) will be unloaded, and the requested page G_i will be loaded instead. The rarely used page is the one for which the usage counter has the minimum value: $M^{\min}_k = \min \{ M_1, M_2, M_3, \dots, M_j \}$.

NRU strategy. In this case, each page has a time counter t_i , which records the number of times the page has been used in the last period. A free memory area is allocated for the page G_i , where it will be placed. If there is no free area in memory, then the page G_j ($i \neq j$) unused in the last period will be unloaded, and instead, the requested page G_i will be loaded. The page is considered unused in the last time for which the number of page usages in the last period has the least value: $B^{\min}_k = \min \{ B_1, B_2, B_3, \dots, B_j \}$.

Based on the given model, algorithms for visualization of virtual memory management have been developed, in particular, algorithms for visualizing page unloading from RAM. Several algorithms have been developed [4, 5]: $L = \{ L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4, L_5 \}$, where: L_1 is the random page unloading algorithm; L_2 is the FIFO algorithm; L_3 is the LRU algorithm; L_4 is the LFU algorithm; L_5 is the NRU algorithm.

Random page unloading algorithm. Initially, there are several pages in RAM. The L_1 algorithm contains the following steps:

1. The first element is read from the page queue, containing the page number (n_i) of the page to be used.
2. The algorithm ends if the element contains "※".
3. If this page is already in memory, it will be

used.

4. If page n_i is not present in memory, then page n_k , $k \neq i$, selected randomly, is unloaded from memory.

5. In the area vacated by page n_k will be loaded page n_i , $A_{si} = A_{sk}$.

6. Move on to the first step.

FIFO algorithm. Initially, there are no pages in RAM, and the PUT (Page Usage Table) is empty. The L_2 algorithm contains the following steps:

1. The pages will be allocated in RAM, and their access numbers (h_i) will be recorded in the PUT.

2. From the page sequence, we read the first element, which contains the number (n_i) of the page to be used.

3. The algorithm ends if the element contains "※".

4. If this page is already in memory, it will be used.

5. If the page n_i is not in RAM, then the first loaded page among the existing ones is unloaded from memory. This is the page for which the entry number has the smallest value: $h^{\min}_k = \min \{ h_1, h_2, h_3, \dots, h_j \}$, $k \neq i$. That is, the n_k page will be unloaded from memory.

6. Page n_i , $A_{si} = A_{sk}$ will be loaded into the area vacated by page n_k .

7. Move on to the second step.

LRU algorithm. Initially, several pages are loaded into the RAM, and the PUT is empty. The L_3 algorithm contains the following steps:

1. From the page sequence, we read the first element, which contains the number (n_i) of the page to be used.

2. The algorithm ends if the element contains "※".

3. If this page is already in memory, it will be used and the time counter for this page will be increased by one: $t_i = t_i + 1$. A corresponding entry will be made in the PUT.

4. If the page n_i is not in RAM, then we will unload the long-unused page from memory. This is the page for which the time counter has the greatest value: $t^{\max}_k = \max \{ t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_j \}$, $k \neq i$. That is, the page n_k will be unloaded from memory.

5. In the area freed by page n_k will be loaded page n_i , $A_{si} = A_{sk}$.

6. Move on to the first step.

LFU algorithm. Initially, several pages are loaded into the RAM, and the PUT is empty. The L_4 algorithm contains the following steps:

1. From the page sequence, read the first element, which contains the number (n_i) of the page to be used.

2. The algorithm ends if the element contains "※".

3. If this page already exists in memory, it will be used, and the usage counter of this page will be increased by one: $M_i = M_i + 1$. A corresponding entry will be made in the PUT.

4. If the page n_i is not in RAM, then will be unloaded from memory the rarely used page. This is the page for which the usage counter has the least value: $M^{\min}_k = \min \{ M_1, M_2, M_3, \dots, M_j \}$, $k \neq i$. That is, the page n_k will be unloaded from memory.

5. In the area freed by page n_k will be loaded page

$n_i, A_{si} = A_{sk}$.

6. Move on to the first step.

NRU algorithm. Initially, several pages are loaded into the RAM, and the PUT is empty. The L_5 algorithm contains the following steps:

1. From the page sequence, read the first element, which contains the number (n_i) of the page to be used.

2. The algorithm ends if the element contains "*".

3. If this page is already in memory, it will be used and the page usage counter will be increased by one: $B_i = B_i + 1$. A corresponding entry will be made in the PUT.

4. If the page n_i is not in memory, then will be unloaded from memory the unused page for the last period T . This is the page for which the number of pages used for the last period T has the least value: $B^{\min_k} = \min \{ B_1, B_2, B_3, \dots, B_j \}, k \neq i$. That is, the n_k page will be unloaded from memory.

5. Page n_i , will be loaded into the area vacated by page $n_k, A_{si} = A_{sk}$.

6. Move on to the first step.

Thus, the article proposes algorithms for visualizing virtual memory management processes. The visualization algorithms are designed for the following strategies for unloading pages from RAM: "Random page unloading", "First in First Out (FIFO)", "Least Recent Unused Page unloading (LRU)", "Least Frequently Used Page unloading (LFU)", "Not Recently Used Page unloading (NRU)". These algorithms work effec-

tively for both processes with equal and unequal priority. Based on the presented algorithms, a software simulator has been developed, which makes it easier for students to understand and study strategies for virtual memory management processes.

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